

Analysis Of The Factors Faced By Female Teachers In Implementing Effective Styles Of Teaching In Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan

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Abstract: Teachers are affected by internal and external factors as they face low salaries, students' behavior, problems in the classroom, injured students with students fight, lack of skill, and other teachers' behavior. In the modern classroom, different teaching styles have been used, such as advanced techniques adopted by today's teachers: formal style, expert style, personal style, delegator style, and facilitator. From a total of 70 girls' high schools in Faisalabad, four schools were selected randomly, and in these schools, 146 female teachers were teaching. The sample size was 106 female high school teachers. A structured questionnaire was used as a research tool for data collection. The collected data were analyzed through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The study concluded that in public high school teaching styles used by teachers in class include lecture method, demonstration, facilitator, hybrid, and group learning. During the class, the teachers face many difficulties such as large class sizes, language barriers, school-related programs, lack of discipline, lack of human resources, and social problems. According to this study, policies for a better school environment are a dire need to uplift the education standard and encouraging teachers for using an effective teaching style.

Keywords: Teacher, Teaching, Styles, Female, Factors, learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

School pioneers improved essentially in their self-detailed information and utilization of education techniques. They announced effectively executed neighborhood workshops, and their members were open and anxious to learn and utilize the showing strategies in their schools [1]. The school chiefs detailed critical difficulties, be that as it may, in executing nearby workshops due to inadequate homeroom assets, troublesome travel conditions to the school locales, and an absence of formal instruction of a considerable lot of the educators [10]. The female teachers were facing many problems working in and outside the home. Teachers faced many problems during teaching. For example, the number of children in the class is more than required; furniture is not available. The teachers used different languages in class. They were facing a mindset environment and traditional norms and values. That is difficult to maintain personal and work life. There are mainly five teaching styles 1: Expert teacher, deliver knowledge and information. 2: Formal is an expert in teaching they follow the tradition and set the rules for the pupil. 3: The personal teacher is using personal examples and suggestions for learner behavior. 4: The facilitator teacher creates personal teaching-learning relations students ask questions and create a class environment independently. 5: The delegator teacher develops and encourages the students to achieve their own goals and learning objectives. Teaching style defines an approach to teach the teacher in class with practice involved in teaching and learning. Teacher teaching styles affect students' learning and education because every student is unique, different in socioeconomic, and belongs to a different cultural

background [6]. There are various interpretations, opinions, and models that measure the concept of learning styles. The classification of the reading style was selected. Two ways to learn that demonstrated various methods of analysis and planning information. This is active-visible and attractive-active, Visual-verbal, and sequential global. The purpose of this study to show the differences in the behavioral performance of the PBL class among active and bright students [1]. Teaching styles should define teacher behavior to show how they interact with students. Five stages of teaching (ideas, digging, development, discovery, and manifestation) and at these stages, students can get an education. Students make on value there, creative activities [9]. Many things and personality traits can influence teaching styles. These things are sometimes so powerful that they can explain the way the teacher teaches in the classroom. Teachers are good leaders for students because their ideas, thinking, ability, skill, knowledge, challenging lessons, manage the classroom, help the students succeed, and increase the students' interest in a class [18]. Teaching styles are based on the needs of teachers, technically personal goals and beliefs; teachers are good at innovation, the achievement of the better student, good at planning, and better performance in examinations. That affects teaching environmental factors, married status, behave, and teaching profession [13]. Females were essentially more arranged toward being viable educators than guys on the center instructor dispositional attributes of instructor adequacy and relational and relational abilities. These discoveries give initial proof utilizing a thorough psychometric methodology to comprehend the huge impact of sex on educating miens [3]. In trying to set up a climate helpful for learning, different school premises regions have been re-developed. These incorporate, for instance, the homerooms, library, nursery, passageways, and bottle. A little performing stage and perusing corner have been incorporated to provide food with a slenderer variety [4]. Instructing for comprehension is predicated on an alternate suspicion about learning. It expects that information is human development and that students must have a functioning impact in altering their perspectives, seeming well and good, interfacing earlier thoughts with new ones, thinking with what they realize and

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imaginatively applying the information in novel circumstances. On the off chance that one tries to encourage this more innovative sort of seeing, at that point, just spreading out the rutted way and directing understudies along the course is insufficient. Rather, instructing turns out to be more a cycle of directing understudies around a space [22]. Teachers are maintaining human resources and quality of life. The teachers aim to provide knowledge, skill, and the basic foundation of education. Teacher in Pakistan has faced many problems like low management, poor transportation system, uncomfortable security, and political issues. Female teachers faced many other problems like sex, age, educational level, and working conditions. Sex and gender discrimination are major factors that affect teaching [11]. Females have consisted of household work in the family. Man is more accessible than females. But the female teachers were facing many problems working outside the home. They were facing a mindset environment and traditional norms and values. That is difficult to maintain a personal and working life. They motivate the family through their job. Sometimes in the job and personal life, women take the stress and go into depression; their mental condition is not good. Women facing many issues and barriers in professional life maintain the balance between home and work life. Women are enjoying personal and work life. Her income is beneficial for family and home needs [8]. The teacher treats his students as objects of influence in the lecture style, not equal participants in the activity. For this reason, the teacher distinguishes himself from the academic team and each student individually. This type of teacher always controls independently. This particular style is more popular in universities. The advantage of the authorization method is that it is a better method during classrooms for older students who need a memoir and do not require teachers' feedback [14]. The hybrid, or blended style, follows an integrated approach to teaching that mixes the personality of the teacher and the needs of students and interests with curriculum-appropriate methods. It enables teachers to tailor the student's needs and their styles to the appropriate subject. Hybrid style trying are many things for all students, prompting teachers to learn too thin and thin [5]. The demonstration method involves teachers showing students how they do something. Students will follow up practicing teacher's demonstrations [21]. Demonstration processes and showings are performed explained Techniques. Thus, demonstrations are a direct means of explaining things to students. It also states that the demonstration is where the teacher shows that something happens by doing. A child learns better through demonstration [17]. Multi-grade instructing can be acknowledged and how it can viably uphold singular understudy learning. The discoveries are discussed concerning educator training with the expectation of expanding the attention to the expert aptitudes required in excellent showing rehearses in multi-grade instructing [7], [9]. The express educational plan made lopsidedness: however, in the long run, it upgraded their self-viability and was useful for them to know about the benefit of serving rustic networks. For example, the shrouded educational program, school instructors, social data, and government contracts recommended the pre-administration educators consider their inspiration, better comprehend their vocation decisions, and increment their estimation of the social utility of educating [23]. Their relationship with educator's melancholy, tension, stress, and fatigue. Along these lines, educators with significant

consideration and low degrees of fix show more prominent depletion, depersonalization, nervousness, and stress. Then again, the profiles that adjust best to weariness, tension, discouragement, and stress compared to instructors with elevated levels of appreciation, consideration, and fix and those with the transcendence of low consideration and high enthusiastic fix. In this way, it appears to be that whatever the situation, improving enthusiastic guidelines is an unmistakable resource in instructor preparing [15].

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Tehsil Faisalabad. This research aimed to identify the factors that affect teaching styles used by female public high school teachers. The study was conducted in Tehsil Faisalabad. Total female public schools in Faisalabad are 70. From these schools, four (4) public schools were taken for study randomly. The population of this study was female teachers who educate in public high schools. There was a total of $N = 146$ teachers in four schools. The sample of the teachers from each school was selected by using a proportionate random sampling technique. The sample size comprising 106 teachers was calculated using www.surveysystem.com with a 95% confidence level and 5% confidence interval. The instrument was a questionnaire. After collecting quantitative data, the data were coded and entered into the computer and analyzed using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). Quantitative data were analyzed through descriptive techniques namely mean, stander deviation and rank orders. However, factor analysis was used to reduce the given methods of teaching currently being used by teachers in high schools, into the groups which are given names according to the nature of methods. Table 1 shows that teachers faced the factor during class. At rank 1st geographical issue faced teachers with a mean value (3.5943) the response rate tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 2nd poor physical facilities with a mean value (3.5943), the response rate tending neutral to agree. At rank 3rd lack of human resource with a mean value (3.5755), the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 4th lack of medical facilities with a mean value (3.5660), the response rate was tending to neutral to agree. At rank 5th absence of headmistress with a mean value (3.5566), the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 6th poor motivation with a mean value (3.5566), the response rate tending neutral to agree. At rank 7th lack of incentive with a mean value (3.5189), the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 8th climate-based issue with a mean value (3.5000), the response tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 9th lack of infrastructure material with a mean value (3.4906), the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 10th lack of security with a mean value (3.4717), the response rate tending neutral to agree. At rank 11th lack of discipline with a mean value (4.0566), the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. The data showed that mostly factor teachers were faced during class. 34.9% of the teachers were faced geographical issues. 29.2% of teachers faced the headmasters were absent during school time. Most teachers worried about poor motivation. This study collected data about teachers who faced the problem while teaching their class. In school, mainly, the issue faced lack of infrastructural material, climate-based issues, lack of security and lack of discipline

Table 1: Perceived factors affecting during class

School-related issues	Mean	S.D	W.S	R.O
Geographical issue	3.5943	1.05811	381.00	1 st
Poor physical facilities	3.5943	1.06707	381.00	2 nd
Lack of human resources	3.5755	1.12925	379.00	3 rd
Lack of medical facilities	3.5660	1.00493	378.00	4 th
Absence of headmistress	3.5566	1.15536	377.00	5 th
Poor motivation	3.5566	1.04271	377.00	6 th
Lack of incentives	3.5189	1.10610	373.00	7 th
Climate based issues	3.5000	1.14018	371.00	8 th
Lack of infrastructural material	3.4906	1.11479	370.00	9 th
Lack of security	3.4717	1.08853	368.00	10 th
Lack of discipline	3.4340	1.16307	364.00	11 th

Likert Scale: 1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neutral 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree

Table 2 shows that teachers faced the factor during class. At rank 1st lack of helping material with a mean value (3.7170), the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 2nd lack of student's interest with mean value (3.6604), the response rate tending neutral to agree. At rank 3rd lack of student's behavior with mean value (3.5755) the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 4th large-sized class with a mean value (3.5755), the response rate was tending to neutral to agree. At rank 5th language barriers with a mean value (3.5377), the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 6th poor curriculum with a mean value (3.4245), the response rate was tending neutral to agree. At rank 7th issue in evaluation with a mean value (3.3962), the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 8th climate-based problem with a mean value (3.5000), the

response tending toward neutral to agree.

Divergences and investigate the result at different levels: strategy, schools, and classes. They, at that point, explore the issues to arise out of these little class activities and assess endeavored arrangements [2]. According to Saricoban and Sakizli [16] were affect the teachers' students' factors teachers, effective lesson design, teacher variables motivating students, teacher's roles and styles, and their voice and body language must play a significant role in classroom management. The data showed that classroom-related problems were teachers faced while implementing the teaching styles. Most teachers believed that those problems faced in her class include issues in evaluation, Poor Curriculum, large class size, and large class size.

Table 2: Mean, stander deviation, weighted score and rank order to classroom-related problems

Classroom related problems	Mean	S. D	W. S	R. O
Lack of helping material	3.7170	1.07575	394.00	1st
Lack of student's interest	3.6604	1.02248	388.00	2nd
Lack of student's behavior	3.5755	1.02305	379.00	3rd
Large class size	3.5755	1.07746	379.00	4th
Language barriers	3.5377	1.10561	375.00	5th
Poor Curriculum	3.4245	1.19482	363.00	6th
Issue in evaluation	3.3962	1.16029	360.00	7th

Table 3 shows that teachers faced personal factors in class. At rank 1st, mentally disturb with a mean value (3.6887), the response rate tending toward often to agree. At rank 2nd psychological issue with a mean value (3.6792), the response rate was tending neutral to agree. At rank 3rd health issue with a mean value (3.6604), the response rate tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 4th financial problems with a mean value (3.6321), the response rate was tending to neutral to agree. At rank 5th promotion-related issue with a mean value (3.6321), the response rate tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 6th promotion-related issue with a mean value (3.6226), the response rate was tending neutral to agree. At rank 7th depression with a mean value (3.5755), the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 8th lack of confidence with a mean value (3.5660), the response tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 9th lack of ownership with a mean

value (3.5377), the response rate tending toward neutral to agree. According to Nadeem et al., [12], this previous study result was compared with the current study on the teachers' mental stress effect of the performance (43%). According to Kushi et al., [8] females consist of household work in the family. Man is more accessible than females. But the female teachers facing many problems working outside the home. They were facing a mindset environment and traditional norms and values. That is not easy to maintain a personal and working life. They motivate the family through their job. Sometimes in the position and personal life, women take the stress and go into depression; also, their mental condition is not good. The data showed that teachers were faced personal factors during class. Females consist of household work in the family. They are facing a mindset environment and traditional norms and values. They were facing psychological issues, health issues, lack of confidence, and depression.

Table 3: Perceived teachers faced the personal factor in class

Personal factor	Mean	S.D	W.S	R.O
Mentally stress	3.6887	1.07228	391.00	1st
Psychological issues	3.6792	1.15096	390.00	2nd
Health issues	3.6604	1.18633	388.00	3rd
Lack of decision making	3.6321	1.12399	385.00	4th
Financial problem	3.6321	1.20574	385.00	5th

Promotion related issue	3.6226	1.13350	384.00	6th
Depression	3.5755	1.09499	379.00	7th
Lack of confidence	3.5660	1.12138	378.00	8th
Lack of ownership	3.5377	1.15614	375.00	9th

Table 4 shows that teachers faced the factor family problem in class, at rank 1st family stress with a mean value (3.5943) the response rate tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 2nd domestic duties with a mean value (3.5849), the response rate tending neutral to agree. At rank 3rd family discouragement with a mean value (3.5849), the response rate tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 4th lack of home environment with a mean value (3.5660) the response rate tending to neutral to agree. A teacher's work is not just a job because it is related to the mind of people. The teacher must put his emotional, family, financial, and career problems in the underlying layers and when he enters the class, his

appearance looks as though everything is okay. This does not come from any knowledge and experience. But what all students share at all levels requires inspiration and interest in the classroom. It is very significant to know how the teacher is in the student's mind [20]. The data showed that the teachers faced family factors in class. Mostly time teachers' minds work on two sides in her class and home hold deities. Currently were mind worried and did not do were duties properly like, family discouragement, lack of home environment, domestic duties pressure and family stress.

Table 4: Mean, standard deviation, weighted score and rank order to family stress

Family problems	Mean	S.D	W.S	R.O
Family stress	3.5943	1.19346	381.00	1st
Domestic duties pressure	3.5849	1.16184	380.00	2nd
Family discouragement	3.5849	1.19418	380.00	3rd
Lack of home environment?	3.5660	1.22683	378.00	4th

Table 5 shows that teachers faced a social problem. At rank 1st sexual harassment faced teachers with a mean value (3.6415) the response rate tending toward often to agree. At rank 2nd violence with a mean value (3.6415), the response rate tending neutral to agree. At rank 3rd relative's interference with mean value (3.5000), the response rate was tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 4th unfavorable community norms with a mean value (3.4906), the response rate tending

to neutral to agree. At rank 5th gender-based issue with a mean value (3.4340), the response rate tending toward neutral to agree. At rank 6th endangered with a mean value (3.4340), the response rate was tending neutral to agree. A community issue or problem is a problem that the community has recognized as a problem that prevents the community from functioning at the right level. It is important to understand that not all social events are elevated to social problems [19].

Table 5: Mean, standard deviation, weighted score and rank order to a social problem

Social problems	Mean	S. D	W.S	R.O
Sexual harassment	3.6415	1.14799	386.00	1st
Violence	3.6415	1.08837	386.00	2nd
Relatives interference	3.5000	1.16496	371.00	3rd
Unfavorable community norms	3.4906	1.08008	370.00	4th
Gender based preference	3.4340	1.15486	364.00	5th
Endangered	3.4340	1.07808	364.00	6th

The factor analysis was done to know the teaching styles of the female teachers. It is a fact that already established styles are not completely followed. This era of social media and the internet has different demands and many teachers establish their way of teachings in their own style. So the most famous

known methods and ways of teachings were enlisted and data was collected on 21 items. The factor analysis was done and three-factor groups were extracted as shown in table no 6 below.

Table 6: Rotated Component Matrix^a

Items	Component			
	Students Participatory teaching	Established patterned teaching	Class Environment management	Room
Conduct class discussion	.849	.134	.200	
Utilize friendly environment with students to students	.782	.102	.280	
Equally treated with individual	.738	.331	.188	
Good result from them	.728	.263	.246	
Use audiovisual material	.705	.463	.015	
Regularly check their work	.701	.241	.320	
Use different technology	.692	.335	.284	
Task complete with easily	.634	.321	.310	
Reorganized sequence of task when need	.628	.530	.079	
Utilize friendly environment with students' teachers	.628	.167	.460	
Sequence of task easily covered	.505	.447	.260	
Used five senses both teachers and students	.267	.818	.183	
Interaction with peers to peers friendly	.302	.722	.218	

New knowledge is created from the already established structure	.107	.682	.494
Use positive reinforcement of students	.556	.602	.065
Setting arrangement according to students needs	.301	.591	.379
Interaction with teachers easily	.492	.562	.274
Conducive learning environment in classroom	.294	.033	.886
Activities in class encourage students to develop their own ideas about content issue	.216	.165	.875
Prepare lesson plan	.222	.314	.770
Allow students mobility	.129	.362	.541

Strongly correlated items, showing high loading values, in a single factor were grouped and, according to the nature of items, were given a name. This way, three teaching styles were extracted: i) Students Participatory Teaching, ii)

Established Patterned Teaching, and iii) Classroom Environment Management. The teacher's distribution according to their own styles is given in table .7.

Table 7: Teachers distribution according to Teaching styles

Types	Frequency	Percent
Students participatory teaching	37	34.9
Established patterned teaching	42	39.6
Class Room Environment management	27	25.5
Total	106	100
Types	Frequency	Percent
Students participatory teaching	37	34.9
Established patterned teaching	42	39.6

The data shows that mostly teachers (39.6%) are using already established patterns of teachings. However, 25.5 percent teachers introduced methods of class room environment management so that student can have effective

learning and 34.9 percent teachers were of view that students participation is essential and they ensured the participation of students in their teaching style

3 CONCLUSIONS

The result showed some problems faced by female teachers in implementing effective teaching styles during classes. These factors had an effect on the teacher during class. Teachers' mental stress, inadequate curriculum, motivation of the teacher to teach, promotion issue, large class size, language barriers, health issue, lack of confidence, social issue, personal factor, and poor class material were the issues identified in this study. Teachers try to create a productive learning environment for students who were learning in a good way and change own life. Those teachers have opted different teaching styles to ensure the effective teaching.

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